

1. Introduction

The government is under pressure, the bureaucratic tradition built in decades is facing a subversive development that threatens its field. Globalization, evolving societies, and growing citizens expect to push governments and public administrations toward a more streamlined, more adaptive organization. Today, it is expected that governments will respond to public needs, manage public funds efficiently and transparently, and adapt to social changes. In this transitional process, public administration gains inspiration from private companies, goal-driven management, and custom. At the same time, the resistance to such a large organizational change is enormous. The huge size of the government makes it slow to change, especially when the implementation of e-government is only one of the many challenges that the government must deal with e-oriented policies [1].

E-commerce and e-Business have been portrayed as brothers and sisters from the private sector and antecedents from e-government [2]. Quite frankly, many transactional and informative phenomena observed in the e-commerce arenas in the private sector seem to be reflected

in e-Government and vice versa. Field/front office work and back-office work in both sectors have also undergone profound changes in the aftermath of the introduction of possibilities and methods that use computer-mediated networks such as the Internet and the Internet. Interestingly, there are few or no studies that record lessons learned and summarize current practices, or establish measures that cross the boundaries of sectors for the success of this rapid socio-technical evolution. However, the organizational and social consequences and consequences in the e-Commerce/e-Government evolution may represent problems that are much more difficult to understand than the admittedly non-trivial (technical) interplay of systems and networks.

The aim of this research is to provide insights into current e-government and e-commerce processes and determine the prospects for companies to meet the industry's growing demand for non-cash payment solutions. To better understand demand issues, such as consumer shopping habits, the geographic scope of companies outside major urban areas, payment acceptance and cash or non-cash use, consumer insight analysis and electronic and mobile commerce Market company survey payment. Companies that support payments, software and logistics services in the industry have conducted surveys to gain insights into the strategies, challenges, and opinions of their businesses' continued growth hurdles.

THE CURRENT STATUS OF THE E-GOVERNMENT PROJECT IN JORDAN AND ITS BENEFITS AND ADVANTAGES

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Abstract: Today, it is expected that governments will respond to public needs, manage public funds efficiently and transparently, and adapt to social changes. In this transitional process, public administration gains inspiration from private companies, goal-driven management, and custom. At the same time, the resistance to such a large organizational change is enormous. The huge size of the government makes it slow to change, especially when the implementation of e-government is only one of the many challenges that the government must deal with e-oriented policies. The quest to implement e-government projects is motivated by the fundamental policy goals of (i) increased effectiveness, efficiency, and information quality; and (ii) improved interaction mechanisms, and in turn better governance tools. In Jordan, e-services initiative is the heart of the e-government. Therefore, the ICT sector is best served and is able to deliver e-government services in an integrated manner, as a result since 2000, many national ICT projects have been launched to sustain and support the e-government program.

Keywords: E-government, system architecture, service delivery, system layers, internet technology, e-administration, smart government, smart technologies.

observations, and participation. In addition, the researcher uses qualitative analysis of an object, a phenomenon or an occurrence to gain information about it or its occurrence. Thus, this research uses an analytical approach to examine and analyze the architectural set up of the e-government system adopted by Jordan.

In addition, the researcher referred to various secondary resources for the collection of information that was relevant to the study. The secondary research allows desk-based study of the required research area. The study could have been taken further by conducting primary research to gain more input for the required system, however due to the time constraint, secondary research was preferred.

3. Results

1. Supporting the e-government strategy to be implemented across governmental entities.
2. Participating in planning and coordinating a national portfolio of e-government initiatives.
3. Maintaining technological integration and interoperability of e-government initiatives and encouraging the reusability of application components.
4. Planning and implementing security policies and a secure network environment.
5. Promoting and monitoring organizational transformation (change management) at the ministry, department, and organizational levels.

6. Educating employees of the government of Jordan and transferring knowledge.

7. Delivering successful e-government initiatives and projects that are managed by dedicated project managers.

8. Providing analysis of, and information on, the status of e-government initiatives and projects to the major stakeholders.

4. SWOT analysis

Strengths. Based on the analysis, it is evident that there is a positive effect of using the e-government in providing services to the public. For instance, when e-government is applied, the citizens obtain services within a short time, they do not have to travel or queue and the costs are reduced. For instance, in Jordan, it has become easy to obtain a driving license, identification certificates and revenue certificates within a short time and without having to travel to the public office to collect them. **Weaknesses.** Nevertheless, it is evident that building, implementing and sustaining the new system requires a lot of resources and technological know-how. **Opportunities.** The e-government system in Jordan is easy to improve by improving both technology and infrastructure, which means that it will continue to be better for the citizens. **Threats.** By using e-government systems, Jordan is over-relying on technology. As such, it is prone to information threats such as phishing, hacking and malicious programs, and viruses.

4. 1. The study problem

There is no doubt that the existence of electronic government contributed to the development and facility of electronic trade applications. And from this aspect, the problem of the current study emerged in an attempt to answer the main question of the study: “What is the effect of transiting from traditional government to electronic government on electronic trade-in Jordan?”

Study Model: the study model was done by the researcher in an attempt to analysis the study problem and links between its hypotheses.

Fig. 1. Study Model (Source: Shirish, 2016)

4. 2. The study significance

The study is considered greatly significant and subsidiary as it is important for governments in general, then to the commercial sector, and last for average people, as follow:

1. Significant to the government, where the government can focus on electronic procedures that contribute to the benefit of the commercial sector.

2. It is considered significant to the commercial sector, where the commercial sector can use electronic government concepts in the development and enhancement of electronic government concept.

3. The study is considered significant to the individuals themselves, where these individuals benefit from achieving their purchase easily and in a short time with no effort or waste of time, whether in the way of figuring out the item or the payment method.

5. Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: The level of ICT infrastructure in a country is closely related to the development of its e-government.

Hypothesis 2: The level of ICT infrastructure in a country is positively related to the development of e-commerce.

Hypothesis 3: The quality of human capital in a country is positively related to the development of e-government.

Hypothesis 4: The quality of human capital in a country is positively related to the development of its e-commerce.

Hypothesis 5: The environmental quality of a country is positively related to the development of its e-government.

Hypothesis 6: The environmental quality of a country is positively related to the development of its e-commerce.

Hypothesis 7: The development of a country’s e-government is positively related to the development of its e-commerce.

Hypothesis 8: The development of a country’s e-government is positively related to the company’s competitiveness.

Hypothesis 9: The development of e-commerce in a country is positively related to the company’s competitiveness.

5. 1. E-government Goals

The main goal is to reduce or exterminate delays and intermediaries between the government and citizens or businesses which raises the costs and restrain delivery of government services [5]. Furthermore, the e-government project aims at improving public service delivery and access to information and services by providing efficient dissemination and management of information to the citizen, increasing government transparency and accountability, and empowering the citizens through allowing them ready access to information and participation in public and policy decision-making [6].

Advantages and benefits of implementing e-government programs and projects mentioned that e-government projects can serve a variety of ends, including better delivery of government services to citizens [7], improved interactions with business and industry, empowerment of citizens through access to information, or more efficient government management. The resulting benefits of e-government projects can be diverse and long-lasting and will encompass less corruption, increased transparency, greater convenience, revenue growth, and/or cost reductions. A number of researchers [8] highlighted that e-government projects have the

following critical benefits to countries, especially the developing countries:

1. Citizens' empowerment. The e-government potentially empowers individual citizens by providing them with a range of services and alternative channels such as the Internet, call centers, faxes, and kiosks for accessing information and services and interacting with the government.

2 Efficiency and effectiveness gains. The e-government can transform the public sector's processes that change the way in which government performs business so as to function as truly citizen-centric government, thus ensuring process efficiency and effectiveness.

5. 2. The Current Status of the E-Government Project in Jor

The e-Government initiative in Jordan has been one of a number of ICT-related initiatives launched with the succession of King Abdullah II to the throne in 1999, which aims at transforming the country into a knowledge-based economy e-services initiative is the heart of the e-government of Jordan [9]. Therefore, the ICT sector is best served and is able to deliver e-government services in an integrated manner. Since 2000, many national ICT projects have been launched to sustain and

support the e-government program [10]. Some examples of these projects are:

1. Implementation of a Secure Government Network (SGN) within 18 government entities.

2. Establishment of the Contact Center that serves the SGN.

3. Launching an Information Security Road Map.

4. Conducting training programs like the ICT literacy and project management programs.

5. Launching an e-government portal in 2006 that integrates all government entities in a seamless manner and which aims at providing users with governmental information and services.

6. Discussion and conclusions

This article summarizes the findings of an empirical pilot on this subject, which brings to the surface various expected and some surprising differences and similarities between e-Commerce and e-Government. The learned respective lessons, current practices and success statistics can benefit both sectors and both evolutionary paths. A deeper understanding of the complex loopholes of technological, organizational and social factors and processes in both e-commerce and e-government can lead to practice-relevant cross-fertilization and reduction of unnecessary reduplication.

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